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PHYTO-ACCUMULATORS TO MITIGATE MICRONUTRIENT DEFICIENCY IN ORGANIC FARMING

Adarsh S.¹, Sithin Mathew², Giffy Thomas³,
Roshni A. S.⁴, Gopika K. T.⁵ and V. Nirosha⁶ and Arya A. P.⁷

¹Department of Agronomy, Kerala Agricultural University, Kerala

²ICAR – Directorate of Floricultural Research, Pune, Maharashtra

³Department of Agriculture, Carmel College, Mala, University of Calicut, Kerala

⁴Department of Botany, Christian College Kattakada, University of Kerala

^{5,6,7}Kerala Agricultural University, Kerala

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ABSTRACT

Subsistence farming in India was shifted to demand driven agriculture for green revolution which includes the use of high yielding varieties, synthetic chemical fertilizers, pesticides, herbicides and other continual inputs in order to achieve a high and consistent crop yield. Though this so called 'conventional' agriculture increases per-area food production, it drains natural resources and impair the quality of both crops and the environment. In contrast, organic farming uses cultural and biological inputs instead of synthetic fertilizers and chemicals for crop nutrition and pest management. Deficiency and imbalance of all essential nutrients is a serious problem in organic farming, especially for crops which need different nutrients in varying proportions. Providing essential nutrition from organic sources is a real challenge. This lacuna can be answered by phyto-accumulators/ phyto-extractors. These are the plant species which have the capacity to absorb and accumulate specific nutrient elements from soil. Identification of plant species with high micronutrient uptake will be useful for crop nutrient management in organic farming. Use of this plant biomass in the form of green manure, mulch or as compost can solve the riddle of micronutrient deficiency in organic farming. Plant growth depends on the amount of nutrients present in biomass. However, there is considerable difference between species than crops in the amount of nutrients present in the biomass, due to the differential ability of species to accumulate nutrients for growth. *Glyricidia maculeata*, *Calatropis gigantea*, etc are popular for their high nutrient content. These plants are useful to correct deficiency of specific nutrients. Also, the roots of phyto-accumulators absorb nutrients from chemical pollutants from soil, and water, thus it acts as an uptake removal mechanism of those otherwise near to impossible removable chemicals. Hence, a vegetative green lush is made by converting non-cultivable area to a cultivable one.

Keywords: Phyto-accumulators; organic farming; micronutrient deficiency; green revolution.

Conventional agriculture

Synthetic agri-chemicals, other continuous inputs, genetically modified organisms (GMOs), concentrated animal feedings, heavy cultural practices, or monoculture production includes conventional agriculture (Azadi *et al.*, 2010; Gomiero *et al.*, 2011; Pufpaff *et al.*, 2021) which is resource- and energy-intensive, and extremely productive (Carlsson-Kanyama and Linden., 2001; Hajer *et al.*, 2016; Gashahun *et al.*, 2021). The challenge of providing food for 11 billion people who are predicted to populate the earth by the end of the century demands such practices (Gleick, 1998;

Borlaug, 2002; Williams *et al.*, 2021). Conventional agriculture provides 98.9% of the world's food (Tal, 2018; and Goel *et al.*, 2021) and this mode of cultivation is relatively young in human history (Tal, 2018; Zerubavel and Zerubavel, 2003; and Parsons, 2021). Fritz Haber invented a mechanism for mixing nitrogen and hydrogen to make ammonia as a synthetic fertiliser, only a century ago (Stoltzenberg, 2004; Renner *et al.*, 2015; Steininger, 2021). Pesticide use was minimal before World War II (Russell, 1999; Dunlap, 2014; and Anstead, 2021). Conventional agriculture allows food production in greater quantities on less area with

lesseffort (Reganold and Wachter, 2016; and Boyd *et al.*, 2021) with heavy machinery, large plots of land, and advanced technology (Kaygusuz, 2011; Lavers, 2012; Kasai, and Rdhadhika, 2021) to gain revenue (Buck *et al.*, 1997; Jarosz, 2008; and SB, 2021) since it necessitates large amount of capital to operate (Berends and Romme, 2001; Woodhouse, 2010; and Oshima, 2021) as agri-chemicals are used to meet the demand for production and yields (Gouda *et al.*, 2018 and Santos *et al.*, 2021). With rising food prices and millions going hungry throughout globally, there lies a moral obligation to feed them through conventional farming at low cost (Reganold and Wachter, 2016; and Throup *et al.*, 2021) since conventional farmers can use cheap synthetic chemicals (Case *et al.*, 2017; and Moinard *et al.*, 2021) to cultivate their crops over a broader area of land, allowing them to sell as needed (Woodhouse, 2010; and Wani, 2021) as the production is more (Frieden and Rogowski, 1996; and Sunny *et al.*, 2021). Crop rotation, intensive farming, polyculture, infrastructure development (as for e.g. proper road connectivity is critical for the delivery of products (Fleischmann *et al.*, 2000; Rahim *et al.*, 2021)) contribute to a better profit margin, thus making conventional farming a profitable option (Stockdale *et al.*, 2001; and Shrestha *et al.*, 2021) and it even provide more jobs (Kalantari *et al.*, 2018; Winkler *et al.*, 2020). Increased food production, will maintain prices, resulting in a win-win situation for both farmers and consumers (Porter, 1989; He, *et al.*, 2020) and even creates opportunities for import (Bellows and Hamm, 2001; Kalogiannidis and Melfou, 2020).

Commercial farming has significant drawbacks, such as deforestation, single crop production, use of chemicals fertilisers (creates poor soil management (Vejan *et al.*, 2016)) which are harmful to human health (Horrigan *et al.*, 2002 and Kasai, and Rdhadhika, 2021). Conventionally grown crops have 18-69 percent lower antioxidants, four times pesticide residues, and have 48 percent higher heavy metal concentrations than organically grown (Gomiero, 2018; Saffeullah *et al.*, 2021). Animals for food production fed mass-produced feeds, which can be detrimental (Focken *et al.*, 2006; Davidowitz, 2021). Preservation of crops demands further financial assistance, or else the producer will be overburdened (Skaperdas, 2001; Giri *et al.*, 2021) hence, demand and supply must be balanced (Syrbe and Grunewald, 2017; Karekatti and Tiwari, 2021). Induced allergies from GMOs (Kramkowska *et al.*, 2013; Raspor and Cingel, 2021), need for huge farming land (Tscharrntke *et al.*, 2012; Kearl and Webster, 2021), deforestation (Kremen and Miles, 2012; Durrer *et al.*, 2021), carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide from heavy machinery (Fan *et al.*, 2009; and World Health Organization, 2021), water pollution (Tal, 2018), eutrophication (Kleinman *et al.*, 2015), chemical leaching (Fuglie, 1999), land degradation (Batistella and Valladares, 2009), diminishing water tables (Foley *et al.*, 2005), and biodiversity loss (González-Chang *et al.*, 2020) are all unavoidable outcomes of conventional agriculture.

Organic Agriculture

Organic farming involves integrating cultural, biological, and mechanical methods that encourage resource cycling, eco system, and biodiversity conservation (Duru *et al.*, 2015; and Bisht *et al.*, 2021) through crop rotation, animal and plant manure as fertilisers, occasional hand weeding (Adarsh and Thomas, 2019a; Adarsh and Thomas 2019b; Adarsh *et al.*, 2019), and biological pest management instead of synthetic fertiliser (Bijarniya and Rayaz, 2020; Antošovský *et al.*, 2021). It is an alternative to conventional agricultural practices (Patil *et al.*, 2014; Saffeullah *et al.*, 2021) as it encourages resource sustainability and aids in the mitigation of climate change, according to the UN's Codex Alimentarius Commission (Codified Agricultural System) for Food and Drugs (Gomiero *et al.*, 2011; Uhumamure *et al.*, 2021). It is based on the idea that soil, plants, animals, and humans are all interconnected (Lund and Röcklinsberg, 2001; Groszlik *et al.*, 2021) and it is ideal for agriculture because it does not require any additives or excessive quantities of water (Kirchmann and Bergström, 2001) which does not deplete soil's resources (Gattinger *et al.*, 2012) by preserving biological variety and refilling of soil productivity (Khanal, 2009) by preferring crop rotation, natural predators, biological pest, disease, and weed management (Adarsh and Thomas, 2019a; Adarsh and Thomas 2019b; Adarsh *et al.*, 2019), and resistance varieties over agrochemicals (Lammerts van Bueren *et al.*, 2002). It is founded on the interplay of soil, plant, animal, human, ecological, and environmental factors (Aeberhard and Rist, 2009) whose primary foundations are organic threshold criteria, dependable systems for certification and government relations, technology modules, and, finally, an efficient and sustainable market infrastructure (Narayanan and Narayanan, 2005). It must maintain and improve the health of the land, plant, animal, human, and planet as a whole (Borron, 2006) and must be handled with prudence and responsibility to protect present and future generations' health and well-being, as well as the environment (Assessment, 2005). It aims to generate an inclusive, secure, and financially viable agriculture with the highest allowable use of renewable energy sources (Rasul, 2016) and to achieve a satisfactorily high productivity, connectivity of cultivation with the circadian rhythms of the entire product lifecycle and long-term fertility and bioactivity of the soil (Niggli, 2007). The elements of organic farming includes crop and soil management (Ghorbani *et al.*, 2009), composting of all biowaste (Füleky and Benedek, 2010), tillage, crop rotation, manure management, usage of cover crops, mulches, and green manuring (Brozyna *et al.*, 2013), domestic and industrial waste recycling (Moeller *et al.*, 2018), and use of microbial inoculants (Pylak *et al.*, 2019). The key advantages of organic agriculture include reduction of exposure to chemicals (Miet *et al.*, 2017), high nutritive value of crops and taste (Reganold and Wachter, 2016), soil health benefits

(Seufert and Ramankutty, 2017), reduces pest infestations (Kilcher, 2007), cost-effective (Dabbert, 2003), and promotes a healthier relationship with the natural environment (Nandwani and Nwosisi, 2016). Farmers in India must adopt a larger range of strategies to maximise nutrient and energy outputs while reducing risk (Aggarwal *et al.*, 2004; Sekaran *et al.*, 2021). These include crop rotations and increased crop diversity, symbiotic nitrogen fixation with legumes and organic manure utilisation (Vance, 2001; Jensen *et al.*, 2020). Sir Albert Howard was a significant figure in the organic industry that emerged after the industrial revolution (Howard and Cie, 1950; Howard, 2021).

Organic farmers must maintain a balance between inputs and outputs in order to minimise nutrient depletion and pollution (Goulding *et al.*, 2009; Khan and Rehman, 2022). This is achieved primarily through the control of organic materials such as crop residues and green manures. Recycling organic matter, enriching compost, vermicomposting, animal manure and urine can all help to keep soil fertility high (Chatterjee *et al.*, 2017; Kelova *et al.*, 2021). Farm Yard Manure (FYM) from the farm enhances soil quality and is utilised as a natural fertiliser in agriculture (Tadesse *et al.*, 2013; Nazir *et al.*, 2021). It expands the ability of the soil to retain more moisture and nutrients. Farmyard manure typically contains 2.3 percent calcium, 0.92 percent magnesium, 803.6 ppm iron, 1312 ppm manganese, 132.4 ppm zinc, and 30.8 ppm copper. Compost is made up of a variety of materials that are used to enrich and enhance soil (Van Elsas and Postma, 2007; Braun *et al.*, 2021). The degradation process is facilitated by slicing the plant waste, adding water, and rotating the container on a regular basis - this ensures optimum aeration and decommissioning. Oil cakes are the solid remnants of the seed after the oil has been extracted. Edible oilseed cakes are primarily utilised as poultry and animal feed, while non-edible ones are used as concentrated manure for livestock and other plants to decompose in a controlled environment (Mohanty *et al.*, 2021). Panchagavya, a natural product, has the capacity to promote growth and provide resistance (Raghavendra *et al.*, 2014; Reddy and Menon, 2021). The abundance of fermentative microbes such as yeast and lactobacillus could be owing to a combination of low pH, milk products, and jaggery/sugarcane juice. Dasagavya is a concoction made up of 10 different items, including panchagavya and plant material. When blended properly, it has remarkable impact on plant growth. The ingredients include cow's dung, urine, milk, curd, and ghee (De and De, 2019; Narayanan and Ishwarya, 2019). Vermiwash is a honey coloured aqueous extract of vermicompost and earthworm interface washings. The earthworms create burrows in worm-worked soils, which are teeming with bacteria. Nutrients from these excavations are washed to the roots, where they are absorbed by plants (Zambare, *et al.*, 2008; Nair, 2021). Compost tea is a nutrient-dense, well-balanced fertiliser made by processing

compost in water. This fertiliser can be used to boost the development, blooms, and yields of floral plants, vegetables, houseplants, and a variety of crops (Whitney *et al.*, 2017; Moreno, 2021). Biofertilizers are living microorganisms that infiltrate the rhizosphere or inside of the plant and encourage development by increasing the availability to the host plant when applied to seeds, plant surfaces, or soil (Mishra and Dash, 2014; Zvinavashe *et al.*, 2021). Farmers are unaware of how to make compost using technological advances and apply them. Farmers must be properly trained in order to produce earthworm compost for contemporary crops (Thu *et al.*, 2012; Autio *et al.*, 2021). Farmers are sceptical that organic materials can provide all minerals in significant amounts (Ly *et al.*, 2012; Jung *et al.*, 2021). After harvest, harvest trash that is useful for decomposing earthworms is collected from the farm and used as animal feed and fuel. Organic farming is becoming more challenging due to rising population explosion.

Phytoremediation and Phyto-accumulators

Phytoremediation is a low-cost, plant-based environmental remediation technology. It uses plants to remove, transport, balance out, or maybe eradicate contaminants in the soil and groundwater (Cunningham *et al.*, 1997; Rezanian *et al.*, 2021). The process takes advantage of plants' ability to concentrate elements and chemicals from the environment. Phytostabilization is the use of specific plant species to immobilise pollutants in the water and soil (Wong, 2003; Li *et al.*, 2021). This method slows the passage of toxins and prevents them from reaching the groundwater. The method can also be used to treat polluted land regions caused by mining and to resolve issues with disposal of wastes. Phytovolatilization is the process by which plants absorb organic pollutants from the soil, transform them to volatile forms, and then discharge them into the environment (Kumar *et al.*, 2018; Meena *et al.*, 2021). Fast-growing trees are especially beneficial in the process of rapid pollutant uptake. Experimental permission has been gained for the use of genetically edited varieties of plant species with high transpiration pull as a viable option for pollution removal. The destruction of contaminants by metabolic pathways in plants is called as phytodegradation or phyto-transformation (Pivetz, 2001; Pandey *et al.*, 2021). Enzyme mechanisms break down complex organic contaminants into smaller molecules, which are then employed as basic components for plant tissue (Suresh and Ravishankar, 2004; Li *et al.*, 2021). Excess fluid encourages several favourable interactions with plants and increases the biodegradation of xenobiotics by various rhizomes dwelling microbial species (Kumar *et al.*, 2020; Ghoghari *et al.*, 2022). Phytoextraction makes use of plants' ability to collect pollutants in the above-ground, useable biomass (Garbisu *et al.*, 2002; Yadav *et al.*, 2021). This relationship entails continuing to gather biomass in order to reduce the accumulation of poisons in the dirt. It can be either a seamless integration (using metal hyper-

accumulating plants or rapidly growing plants) or an activated cycle (utilizing synthetic compounds to build the bioavailability of metals in the soil). Some plants are capable of loading soil or water with extremely high metal intersections, holding these metals via their roots, and concentrating extremely high levels of metals in its tissues (Reichman, 2002; Rai *et al.*, 2021). The ability of specific plants known as hyperaccumulators to bioaccumulate manmade chemicals causes the focusing effect (Sarma, 2011; Oladoye *et al.*, 2021). A plant is said to be a hyperaccumulator when it can pack contaminants at a rate that varies depending upon toxicity (for example, more than 1000 mg/kg of dry load for nickel, copper, cobalt, chromium, or lead) (Malik *et al.*, 2010; Sharma *et al.*, 2021). Hyperaccumulating plants are important because they can extract metals from polluted sites' soils (phytoremediation) (McGrath *et al.*, 2001; Gavrilesco, 2022). There are many plants that are known to accumulate elements from the soil. Arsenic, from sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*), or the Chinese Brake fern (*Pteris vittata*) (Azeem *et al.*, 2017; Piracha *et al.*, 2022). Cadmium and zinc, using alpine pennycress (*Thlaspi caerulescens*) (Benzarti *et al.*, 2010; Monteiro and Soares, 2021). Chromium is toxic to most plants. However, tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum*) show some promise (Piscitelli *et al.*, 2020; Velli *et al.*, 2021). Lead can be created by using Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea*), ragweed (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia*), hemp dogbane (*Apocynum cannabinum*), or poplar trees, which sequester lead in their biomass (Rhodes, 2013; Shukla, *et al.*, 2010). Salt-tolerant (moderately halophytic) barley and sugar beets are commonly used for the extraction of sodium chloride (common salt) to reclaim fields that were previously flooded by seawater (Bernstein, 1975; Grigore, 2021). Caesium-137 and strontium-90 were removed from a pond using sunflowers after the Chernobyl accident (Igwe *et al.*, 2005; Koul and Adlakha, 2021). Phyto extraction methods as a nutrient source in agricultural production has long been recognised, but their value for organic farming has only recently been recognised (Cunningham and Ow, 1996; Saad-Allah *et al.*, 2021). Modern farming systems rely heavily on the outside application of organic nutrients to agricultural crops (Watson *et al.*, 2002; Shah and Londhe, 2020). This is due to the increased need for agricultural products to meet human consumption requirements. Phytoaccumulators are plants that store at least 1000 mg/kg (dry weight) of a particular metal or metalloid (Eze and Harvey, 2018; Abagaet *et al.*, 2021). Hyper accumulator plants have a deep root system and a larger root surface area. *Pistia stratiotes*, *Spirodela polyrhiza*, *Myriophyllum aquaticum*, *Ludwigia palustris*, *Mentha aquatica*, *Eichhornia crassipes*, *Brassica juncea*, *Zea mays*, and *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* are some of the notable hyperaccumulator plants used in phytoremediation. (Kamal *et al.* 2004; Ramana *et al.*, 2021). Genetic modification of plant cells can increase the effectiveness of phytomining, which is the processing and preparation of bioavailable metal species from polluted fields into plant

cells. (Ali *et al.*, 2013; Farooqi *et al.*, 2022). Some of the probable areas of genetic modification in the genomic cells of plants include metallothionein, metal transporters, and oxidative stress pathways. It is a possible commercial use of poisoned fields with little to no ecological consequences (Evans *et al.*, 1992; Heaton *et al.*, 1998; Memon and Schröder, 2009; Patra and Mohanty, 2013). The chloroplast plays a major role in the breakdown of ingested metal into nanoparticles. Some plants can absorb metals from soil and convert them to nanoparticles, and preserve them in their stems, leaves, and roots via their biosynthetic processes (Rehman *et al.*, 2021; Farooqi, 2021). Phytoaccumulation potential of floating macrophytes such as *Limnobium laevigatum* and *Ludwigia peploides* for the restoration of lead and zinc-contaminated water (Haverkamp, 2011; Fernández San Juan *et al.*, 2018; Muthusarayanan, 2020). The creation of metallic nanoparticles inside plant cells was confirmed using UV-visible spectroscopy, EDX, TEM, atomic absorption spectroelectron, and X-ray absorption spectrometry on partitioned plant parts (Dzimitrowicz *et al.*, 2018; ElFaham *et al.*, 2021).

The production of multi-nucleolus, multi-vacuoles, and deposition of metal granules in the cellular component of roots of *P. hysterophorus*, *C. sativa*, *Solanum nigrum*, and *R. communis* was observed under TEM. These native plants could be employed for in situ phytoremediation and eco-restoration of sites damaged by industrial waste (Zayed *et al.*, 1998; Shekhawat and Arya, 2009; Marchiol, 2012). Even in mineral-deficient soils, the PGP (plant growth promoting) feature helps plants develop their root systems (Francis *et al.*, 2010). Plant growth-promoting bacteria change the structure of their roots to allow for efficient nutrient uptake from the soil (Adesemoye *et al.*, 2009). Endophytic microorganisms, such as mycorrhizal fungi, colonise roots and influence iron, zinc, phosphorus, and copper uptake efficiency. (Singh and Prasanna, 2020). Our soils have become nutrient deficient as a result of the green revolution technologies, fueled by high producing cultivars and chemical fertilisers. Farmers preferred mono cropping practises over multi-cropping, organic farming, green manuring, and so on. They used excessive chemical inputs indiscriminately and improperly in their fields, resulting in soil health issues and pollution problems. The necessity of the hour is for agriculture to change its attention from chemical fertiliser to organic manures in order to restore soil health.

Absorption and storage in hyper accumulators

Mercury does not have any physiological activities in plants. It is absorbed from the soil in a non-specific way as dissolved complexes or free ions by binding to phosphates, carbonates, sulphides, and hydroxides (Silveira *et al.*, 2003). Phytotoxic effects of high mercury concentrations on plants are possible. It impacts photosynthesis by disrupting mitochondrial and chloroplast electronic transport mechanisms. Hg also inhibits

the operation of aquaporins, causing plants to absorb less water (Farooq *et al.*, 2009). Lead phytotoxicity is a toxic chemical which limits metabolic processes by interfering with enzymes (Zulfiqar *et al.*, 2019). Root elongation, seed germination, and overall plant growth are all affected by the presence of high levels of lead (Munzuroglu and Geckil, 2002). Some recognised lead hyperaccumulators such as *Brassica napus* and *Euphorbia cheiradenia* accumulate more than 1000 mg of lead per kg dry weight. Apoplastic pathways or calcium channels are involved in lead uptake by roots (Sarwar *et al.*, 2017).

An overabundance of zinc is hazardous, resulting in stunted plant development and slowed metabolism (Onakpa *et al.*, 2018). The family of metal carriers is primarily responsible for transporting it from roots to shoots (Sasaki *et al.*, 2012). Zinc is then delivered to the shoots via xylem sap, where it accumulates as dense electronic deposits in vacuoles (Hu *et al.*, 2009). *Thlaspi caerulescens* and *Arabidopsis halleri* displayed enhanced expression leading in greater zinc uptake (Küpper and Kochian, 2010).

Cadmium is a trace metal which can be deposited on any portion of the plant, limiting growth, creating petioles, and inflorescences (Jones, 1997). Cadmium stress affects plant cell transport systems, limits enzyme activity, and decreases water and nutrient absorption (Liu *et al.*, 2010). Chloroplast microstructure changes, as well as a reduction in the net rate of photosynthesis and transpiration in leaves (Zhanget *al.*, 2014).

At high levels, chromium is known to impede the absorption of NM bases like Fe, Mg, and Ca (Shanker *et al.*, 2005). The uptake of Cr by plants is reduced when sulphur is present in the nutrient media because they're vying for the same transportation lane (Samuel *et al.*, 2021). Plants absorb chromium, which forms a compound with organic acids called Cr, which penetrates progenitor cells symplastically, whereas Cr penetrates them apoplastically (Malaviya *et al.*, 2020).

Copper is required for plant development and growth. The metal is only required in the amounts of 5-20 mg per g per 1 dry weight by a healthy plant (Chaignon and Hinsinger, 2003). Excess metal is poisonous and has a negative impact on plant growth. The roots can quickly absorb copper. Transport across all membranes is mediated by the P-type heavy metal ATPase (Palmgren and Harper, 1999). Copper Transporter Protein (COPT) is involved in the transport of Cu from Cu (I) to the cell and enhances Cu penetration (Shabbir *et al.*, 2020). Toxins on Cu are removed by the hyperaccumulator through two mechanisms: complexation and compartmentalization (Leitenmaier and Küpper, 2013). Cu is only attracted to oxygen ligands. It hinders cytoplasm penetration and dissociates from the vacuole or cell wall,

where it binds to organic acids weakly (Wang and Chen, 2006).

Arsenic (As) is poisonous to plants and is not required for their survival. Herbicides, insecticides, and wood preservatives, as well as irrigation with contaminated water, induce soil and crop contamination (Nagajyoti *et al.*, 2010). Plants like *Cytisus striatus*, *Agrostis capillaris*, *Deschampsia caespitosa*, and *Holcus lanatus* regulate Arsenic intake to avoid toxicity (Gupta *et al.*, 2011). High amounts of phytochelatins accumulate in Arsenic (V) tolerant phenotypes of *Holcus lanatus* and play a crucial role in Arsenic (V) hypertolerance (Bleeker *et al.*, 2006).

CONCLUSION

'Conventional' agriculture drains natural resources and impairs the quality of crops and environment. Organic farming uses cultural and biological inputs instead of synthetic fertilizers and chemicals for crop nutrition and pest management. Plant species with high micronutrient uptake will be useful for crop nutrient management in organic farming. *Glyricidia maculeata*, *Calatropis gigantea*, etc are popular for their high nutrient content. Also, the roots of phyto-accumulators absorb nutrients from chemical pollutants from soil, and water, thus it acts as an uptake removal mechanism.

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